

Support Interventions for Informal Circular Economy: A Case Study from Delhi, India

Aditi Daeyi, Lund University

Abstract

While circular economy (CE) discourse emphasises technology-driven solutions and formal systems, cities in the Global South rely on grassroots waste workers (WWs) in the informal sector, who perform essential circular functions through waste collection, sorting, and recycling. In Delhi, informal WWs contribute substantially to material recovery and fill gaps left by formal solid waste management (SWM) systems. However, they face considerable challenges affecting their health, livelihoods, environmental safety, and dignity, limiting their contributions to circular systems. This article examines how support interventions can enhance grassroots WWs' integration into circular waste management systems while improving their working conditions. Using a qualitative case study approach, the research develops a model of support interventions through systematic analysis of Global South case studies, then tests and refines this model through fieldwork with stakeholders and WWs in Delhi's SWM sector. The study identifies five intervention pathways and argues that small-scale, decentralised interventions leveraging local knowledge can effectively address systemic barriers while maintaining WWs' autonomy. The research contributes to CE literature by supporting inclusive approaches for enhancing both social equity and environmental effectiveness. While findings are specific to Delhi's context, they offer insights for Global South contexts where informal waste systems are central to CE practices.

Keywords

Circular economy, solid waste management, informality, just transitions, Delhi

Introduction

The concept of circular economy (CE) has gained prominence in urban sustainability discourse, emphasising resource efficiency, waste reduction, and sustainable production cycles (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2021; Schröder, Anggraeni, et al., 2019). However, the academic CE discourse has predominantly focused on industrial and technological applications, primarily

Authors:

Aditi Daeyi (*corresponding author*), Lund University, Sweden, aditidaeyi@gmail.com, ORCID: [0009-0008-0787-2633](https://orcid.org/0009-0008-0787-2633).

in the Global North, where formal systems and advanced infrastructure enable implementation on a larger scale, with limited space for grassroots-level innovation (Abunyewah et al., 2023; de Jesus & Mendonça, 2018). In contrast, cities in Global South countries present different dynamics of CE where circularity is already embedded in informal economic activities, especially in the waste management sector (Okyere et al., 2024; Schröder, Anantharaman, et al., 2019).

In these contexts, informal waste workers (WWs) at the grassroots level serve as critical actors in urban resource recovery systems, and yet their contributions remain largely unrecognised in formal CE discourse, while they work in precarious conditions facing social stigma and harassment (Valencia, 2020; WIEGO, n.d.; Wilson et al., 2017). Delhi, India's capital city, presents a compelling case study of this phenomenon. The city's grassroots WWs manage substantial portions of daily waste through collection, sorting, and recycling activities (Chaturvedi & Gidwani, 2010). Their activities, such as waste picking, collection, segregation, and trade, constitute an informal CE system operating in parallel to the municipal solid waste management (SWM) system, often achieving higher material recovery rates compared to formal systems (Gupta, 2012).

Despite their critical role in urban sustainability, grassroots WWs face multiple negative externalities that compromise their health, livelihood security, environmental safety, and dignity. These challenges not only affect individual workers but also limit the potential for scaling CE practices at the grassroots-level (Schröder, Anantharaman, et al., 2019). As cities in the Global South transition towards formal CE frameworks, informal WWs risk exclusion, further marginalisation, and loss of livelihoods (Velis, 2017). This underscores the urgent need for small-scale, decentralised interventions that enhance the worker conditions without imposing the risks of formalisation or exclusion, ensuring just transitions to CE in these urban contexts.

This article addresses a critical gap in the CE literature by examining how support interventions can enhance the grassroots WWs' integration into sustainable waste management systems in the urban Global South context, thereby improving circularity within the system. The research explores bottom-up interventions that recognise and strengthen existing grassroots practices while addressing systemic inequalities and ensuring just transitions, with Delhi as the case study. The study addresses the central question: How can informal CE be improved at the grassroots-level in Delhi? This overarching question is supported by two sub-questions examining what the key negative externalities are impacting grassroots WWs engaged in circular waste management, and how interventions by stakeholders can improve CE practices and reduce these externalities through integration of WWs into institutional waste networks, support for collective action, capacity building for entrepreneurship, equipment provision, and advocacy efforts.

This research contributes to both the theoretical understanding and practical implementation of CE in Delhi. Theoretically, the study advances our understanding of how grassroots CE practices are challenging CE frameworks that prioritise formal and technology-driven solutions. Practically, it provides actionable frameworks for stakeholders working to enhance grassroots CE practices. In terms of policy relevance, the findings inform recommendations for integrating informal grassroots WWs into formal waste management systems while preserving the efficiency and effectiveness of their existing practices. From a social justice perspective, the research addresses important questions about equity and justice in CE implementation, particularly regarding the recognition and support of marginalised workers who contribute significantly to urban sustainability.

While this study focuses on Delhi's context, the insights offer valuable lessons for similar Global South urban contexts where informal SWM systems play critical roles in CE practices, contributing to the growing body of literature that recognises the need for inclusive approaches to CE implementation that prioritise social equity alongside environmental sustainability.

Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

Circular Economy Theory and Critiques

The CE concept has evolved significantly, with Stahel (2016) describing it as a system of reprocessing materials and goods linked to goals of generating jobs, saving energy, and reducing consumption and waste. Geissdoerfer et al. (2017) positioned CE as a regenerative system designed to minimise resource consumption through sustainable strategies. However, the diversity in understanding has led to conceptual fragmentation, with Kirchherr et al. (2017) identifying 114 definitions of CE that often focus disproportionately on environmental dimensions while underrepresenting the social dimension (Homrich et al., 2018). The concept faces criticism for insufficient integration of social theories (Blomsma & Brennan, 2017) and limited capacity to address real-world complexities such as varied stakeholder interests (Korhonen et al., 2018).

Critical perspectives from the Global South lens challenge the conventional understanding of CE by highlighting the exclusion of informal practices and actors from mainstream CE discourse. Schröder et al. (2019) argue for localised CE approaches, emphasising grassroots innovations and participatory governance as essential components of sustainable urban transitions. Abunyewah et al. (2023) noted the limited research investigating the circularity within low-income informal communities, underscoring the necessity for further exploration of CE in such contexts and for enhancing the existing application of circular principles. This gap in research and recognition has implications for both theoretical understanding and practical

implementation of CE in contexts where informal systems play crucial roles in urban sustainability.

Given these criticisms and the potential role of CE in ethical and fair distribution of resources (Upadhyay et al., 2024), the study adopts Okyere et al.'s (2024) definition of CE within informality. Okyere et al. extend the CE discussion to urban informal systems, highlighting the synergies between CE principles and informal waste systems in low-income settings, arguing for a localised approach to CE, emphasising grassroots innovations and participatory governance as essential components of sustainable urban transitions. Following this approach, CE in waste management is understood to refer to activities promoting resource recovery, creating value from otherwise polluting materials, generating income and jobs for participating workers, and improving sustainability in the resource chains by reducing waste generation. This definition recognises both the environmental and social dimensions of circularity, particularly as practised by grassroots actors in informal systems.

Informality and Grassroots

The concept of informality can be understood as a multidimensional spectrum rather than just the binary opposite of the 'formal'. Hart's (1973) early labour market studies described informal work as income-generating activities adopted by low-wage workers that lie both 'in and out' of the labour force and emphasised that informality is a practice rather than a fixed status. International standards later expanded on the definition, defining informal employment as work that falls outside national labour legislation and lacks social protection coverage (ILO, 2023; Hussmanns, 2004). Both Hart and the International Labour Organisation¹ (ILO) emphasise that informal work is just work being carried out under informal conditions that remain outside statutory protections even when it exists within the formal sector, regardless of its scale, level of productivity or legality.

More recent academic discourse expands the concept further as a spectrum of social and cultural arrangement that "precede formalisation, resist articulation in dominant discourses, or deliberately operate outside official rule-books" (Ledeneva, 2018, pp. 1-2) and positions actors in this frame as 'elites' with state endorsed privileges and recognition, and as 'subaltern' groups that suffer stark power and resource asymmetries (Banks et al., 2020). With the notion of power, informality in the Global South can also be viewed as a result of the persistence of colonial attitudes about the market, which equate formalised economy and residency with modernity, while marginalising the existing practices that lie outside these notions as backwards or

¹ ILO is the United Nations (UN) agency which follows the goal of 'promoting social justice and internationally recognized human and labour right'. See more: <https://www.ilo.org/about-ilo>

secondary (Banks et al., 2020). Using different frames of the concept, this paper uses informality as a multi-dimensional concept where work or workers don't always exist in the binaries of formal or informal, rather within the term informality, workers are engaged in practices that may also fall within the formal sector institutions.

In the informal SWM context, grassroots refer to locally anchored, community-driven forms of organisation and experimentation. Grassroots innovations can be simply understood as “social experiments of innovative technologies, values, and institutions” that differ from mainstream practice in their operational forms, such as cooperatives, informal community groups, social enterprises and voluntary associations (Hossain, 2016, p. 3). The knowledge, experience and skills that drive these innovations are embedded in the everyday practices of residents and workers who operate beyond formal training, research and industry systems (Reinsberger et al., 2015, as cited in Hossain, 2016). In contexts where conventional innovation becomes ‘locked-in’, such grassroots initiatives can create niche spaces where sustainable change is possible (Seyfang & Haxeltine, 2012, as cited in Hossain, 2016).

Building on this understanding of the informality and grassroots, this paper adopts the label ‘grassroots informal waste workers’ (or just grassroots WWs) to capture two inseparable features of the informal waste sector in the context of the study. The workers in the study all display grassroots characteristics regardless of their level of informality.² They self-organise into small-scale self-help groups and neighbourhood collectives that coordinate door-to-door collection, on-site sorting and material recovery. These practices are highly localised, low-tech and rely on detailed community knowledge of waste streams, thereby embodying the ‘social experiment’ notion of grassroots innovation. Since the grassroots organisational form is a constant across the sampled workers, it provides a stable frame for the combined label ‘grassroots informal WWs’, which evokes the informal characteristics of their work while also focusing on the locally anchored and community-driven operational design of their work. This label captures both the agency of workers who manage waste from the bottom up and the structural precarity that stems from their informal status.

Grassroots WWs

Several descriptions of grassroots informal workers in the waste sector focus on the term ‘waste picking’. WIEGO³ (n.d.) defines waste pickers as “individuals who collect reusable and recyclable materials (either segregated or mixed) from residential and commercial waste bins,

² Detailed description of the participant WW groups are provided in the section “Delhi Case study: Context and Findings” (pp. 53-57).

³ Women in Informal Employment: Globalising and Organising (WIEGO) is a global network of workers in informal employment. See more: <https://www.wiego.org/>

large generators, dumpsites and public spaces to repurpose or direct these materials to recycling and earn their living”. Dias & Samson (2016) emphasise the diversity within this occupation, explaining that “waste pickers can range from poor people rummaging through garbage in search of food, clothing and other basic, daily needs to informal private collectors of recyclables for sale to middlemen or businesses, as well as organised collectors/sorters of recyclables linked to unions, cooperatives or associations”, with an estimated “1 to 2 per cent of the world’s urban population” earning a living from this work (p.6). While Schröder et al. (2019) characterises them as “individuals, from marginalised social groups of the urban poor, who perform waste collection and recycling activities to obtain a small source of income in order to ensure their survival”, the definition also recognises that “they are highly skilled in identifying materials of value in the municipal waste stream and locating customers within the market” (pp. 58-59).

Moreover, the International Alliance of Waste Pickers (IAWP, n.d.) self-defines the term comprehensively as “individuals involved in collection, segregation, sorting, and sale of recyclables in an informal or semi-formal capacity as own account holders”, which involves activities beyond ‘picking’. IAWP also establishes the dimensions of formality in waste work within the terms ‘informal’, ‘semi-formal’, or ‘integrated into municipal waste management systems’.

However, while ‘waste picker’ typically refers to individuals who collect and sort recyclable materials from streets, dumpsites, or landfills, the broader term ‘waste worker’ (WWs) encompasses a more comprehensive spectrum of roles within the grassroots informal waste economy. As evidenced throughout the literature cited in this section, authors routinely reference WWs even when operationally defining their research subjects as waste pickers, reflecting the recognition that these individuals perform diverse functions beyond ‘picking’, including door-to-door collection, sorting, segregation, transportation, aggregation, and informal recycling. The terminology itself reflects deliberate efforts to move away from derogatory language; at the First World Conference of Waste Pickers in Colombia (2008), a provisional consensus was reached to use the generic term ‘waste picker’ in English to supplant the derogatory term of ‘scavenger’, with the choice emphasising “that these workers perform labour at the bottom of the much larger waste recycling chain” (Samson, 2009, p.2). Recognising these individuals as ‘workers’ rather than merely ‘pickers’ situates them within discourses of labour rights, decent work, and social protection, which are frameworks critical to just transition discussions in sustainability and waste governance (ILO, 2023; Stoevska, 2024). Therefore, for this article, grassroots WWs are defined as individuals or groups engaged in the informal or semi-formal collection, sorting, transportation, resale, and recycling of solid waste, who operate

without formal employment contracts or social protections but perform essential environmental services within urban waste systems.

Informality in the Waste Management Systems

An effective waste management system can be considered the starting point for transition from a linear to CE for a city (Schröder, Anantharaman, et al., 2019), which is also how the CE concept materialises in several cities in the Global South, with practices that may be rooted in traditional knowledge and systems (Gutberlet & Carenzo, 2020). Gutberlet & Carenzo (2020) argued that grassroots WWs in Global South countries have long practised circular resource flow ideas. Their existence often stems from the inadequate capacity of the state to deliver effective public services (Kraft et al. 2016; De Soto 1989 in Coletto and Bisschop 2017, as cited in Estrada et al., 2023).

Grassroots WWs play crucial roles in filling service gaps left by formal waste management systems, providing essential services such as waste collection, segregation, and recycling that contribute to environmental and economic sustainability, and hence circularity (Coletto & Bisschop, 2017). They reduce transportation costs and minimise landfill use, despite their labour being characterised as low-paid, unregulated, and labour-intensive (Chikarmane 2012; Wilson et al. 2006 as cited in Estrada et al., 2023). Korsunova et al. (2022) described these practices as ‘necessity-driven circularity’, highlighting their role in retaining material value and providing livelihoods, beyond the environmental impact. Wilson et al. (2012) reported that material recovery in low-income countries is carried out predominantly by the informal sector at levels which are comparable to the formal material recovery in high-income countries. Noble (2019) cited studies reporting the contribution of the informal sector, consisting of 80,000 workers in cities in the Global South, which resulted in valorising around 3 million tonnes per year of waste.

Environmental and economic contributions of the informal waste sector are evident across the Global South, with examples like Dharavi in Mumbai (India) generating approximately 1 billion USD through recycling activities (Marino, 2021) while saving city authorities over USD 50 million in 2009-2010 and more than USD 80 million in 2010-2011 in avoided municipal costs (Wilson et al., 2012). Despite substantial contributions, grassroots WWs face systematic exclusion from formal systems through restricted material access due to privatisation, income insecurity, and lack of policy recognition. This exclusion is exemplified by cases such as Cairo’s Zabaleen collectors who lost income when private recycling startups modernised waste management without their integration (Littlewood et al., 2022), and Delhi’s informal workers who experienced reduced access and employment opportunities following sector privatisation (Schindler et al., 2012).

Grassroots WWs face multiple negative externalities across four interconnected dimensions: health, livelihood security, environmental safety, and dignity. These challenges include health risks from exposure to hazardous materials and lack of protective equipment leading to respiratory problems and injuries (Banthia Mahesh & Mukherjee, 2019; S. Dias & Samson, 2016; Gutberlet & Uddin, 2018), income instability due to market fluctuations and middlemen exploitation (S. Dias & Samson, 2016; Ezeudu et al., 2021; Reddy, 2015), environmental hazards affecting both workers and their surroundings with limited access to safe working spaces (de Azevedo et al., 2018; Okyere et al., 2024), and dignity issues concerning lack of recognition, autonomy, and social stigma attached to their work (S. Dias & Samson, 2016; Palm et al., 2024; Singh, 2021).

Just Transitions Framework

The challenges of the CE application in Global South cities necessitate 'just transitions' which emphasise inclusive and equitable socio-economic transformations, particularly for marginalised workers in grassroots SWM. While CE presents sustainability and economic growth opportunities, implementation often disproportionately benefits formalised sectors, sidelining informal economy operators and negatively impacting many workers and industries, which can also result in wage inequalities and worker displacement (Schröder, 2020; Velis, 2017). Grassroots WWs face significant risks of exclusion as cities transition towards more formal SWM systems (S. Dias & Samson, 2016; Gutberlet & Carenzo, 2020).

Just transitions principles ensure WWs are supported, rather than displaced through policies that formalise their roles, without eliminating their livelihoods (Schröder, 2020). Adopting a more synergetic approach can lead to new opportunities that help prevent the reinforcement of existing inequalities during the implementation of CE practices in informal economies and promote a just sustainability transition (Abunyewah et al., 2023). Institutionalising multi-stakeholder governance models, including WWs, policymakers, NGOs, and the private sector, can create more resilient and socially inclusive CE systems (S. Dias & Samson, 2016; Schröder, Anantharaman, et al., 2019).

The goal for CE transitions is not to push formalisation but to provide formal support, preventing adverse impacts on workers and the environment (Abunyewah et al., 2024). Just transitions emphasise social equity, decent work, and environmental justice, particularly for marginalised groups like grassroots WWs (Schröder, 2020). The just transitions framework is particularly relevant in this study as it aligns with the contextual situation in the Global South, where the risk of formalised tech-driven solutions has the potential to negatively impact the sizeable informal sector of workers. This framework provides a lens to evaluate exclusionary

practices and explore pathways for integrating grassroots WWs without displacement (Abunyewah et al., 2024).

Just transitions in CE transitions can be introduced at the 'end-of-first-life' stage of the supply chain by improving the conditions for grassroots WWs, especially by addressing the externalities faced by them in terms of health, safety and livelihood security (Schröder, 2020). Abunyewah et al. (2023) and Schröder et al. (2019) theorise approaches of improving CE application in the Global South through 'stakeholder engagement' and 'actor-centric frameworks' which emphasise the roles and interactions of various stakeholders, such as NGOs and policymakers, who can support transitions from linear to circular models while focusing on unique socio-economic contexts of different cities and communities by creating synergies between stakeholder at different levels. Support interventions by key stakeholders for grassroots WWs can be used as a tool for alleviating the externalities faced by the workers, and hence, improving the application of the CE concept in cities in the Global South.

The study argues that interventions to support grassroots WWs and their contributions to CE are crucial for retaining the circularity of SWM in cities. The activities of these workers in cities in the Global South are critical to the circularity in SWM and the cities themselves. Without their input, the SWM in these cities would lose circularity in the waste flow, as the formal sector systems, both public and private, have not been able to facilitate an effective SWM system. Abunyewah et al. (2024) argued that such approaches are essential for achieving equitable transitions to CE, emphasising the need for inclusive policymaking and resource allocation. The framework emphasises that enhancing the livelihoods, dignity, and working conditions of WWs is not only essential for maintaining urban circularity but also for ensuring just transitions to CE. This approach argues for the necessity and effectiveness of small-scale, decentralised support interventions that leverage local knowledge and address the systemic challenges faced by informal WWs, while aligning with broader sustainability goals.

Research Gap and Contributions

While there is growing recognition of grassroots WWs' contributions to CE systems, significant gaps remain in understanding how to effectively support these workers through systematic intervention frameworks. Most CE research focuses on top-down applications, while WW practices in the Global South showcase deeply embedded circular practices that are frequently overlooked in mainstream CE discourse. This disconnect limits understanding of how to design interventions that simultaneously enhance grassroots workers' conditions and CE outcomes.

This study addresses these gaps by developing a systematic model of support interventions that integrates multiple pathways for supporting grassroots WWs within CE frameworks. The research contributes to the discussion by combining good practice examples from Global South case studies with practical insights from testing the model in Delhi's context. The proposed model outlines five intervention pathways that prioritise support from key actors to empower WWs and foster circular innovation, arguing that small-scale, decentralised interventions leveraging local knowledge can effectively address systemic challenges while aligning with broader sustainability goals.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employs a qualitative case study approach, integrating a literature-based model of support interventions at the grassroots level with qualitative data from Delhi's SWM sector. The research followed a two-phase structure: first, developing a literature-based framework through systematic analysis of Global South case studies; and second, testing and refining the framework through investigation of Delhi's grassroots SWM context. This approach enabled both theoretical contributions through model development and practical insights gained from testing the model in the case study.

Literature Review Method

The literature-based model was developed through a systematic review of documented support interventions for grassroots WWs across Global South cities. Literature-based case studies were selected through keyword literature searches on Google Scholar and reference examination from relevant literature, focusing on interventions that aimed at alleviating the negative externalities faced by WWs in terms of health, environment, livelihood, and dignity. The analysis involved four structured steps: documentation of case studies, thematic analysis to identify common patterns of interventions, categorisation into pathways based on intervention types, and creation of tabular and visual models to organise findings systematically (Figure 1 and Appendix 1). This process identified five distinct pathways for support interventions: building networks of stakeholders to include WWs, forming and strengthening WW cooperatives, capacity strengthening for entrepreneurship, access to equipment and technology for remanufacturing and production, and advocacy for grassroots WWs' contribution to SWM. The pathways were adapted from Buch et al. (2021), who identified four pillars for achieving 'inclusive CE solutions for WWs', and a fifth pathway of 'support through advocacy' was added, based on the literature-based case studies.

In-depth Case Study Selection and Fieldwork

Delhi was selected as in-depth case study for its representation of Global South urban SWM challenges and its complex environment for grassroots WW groups. Delhi's context includes supportive national policies that recognise informal workers and implementation challenges at the municipal SWM level. The city's stakeholder ecosystem, including established NGOs, research organisations, private sector initiatives, and worker cooperatives, offers multiple perspectives on support intervention implementation. Given the complex nature of informality in the context, the study focused on three distinct groups of grassroots WWs operating in different contexts within Delhi's SWM system, allowing for analysis of varying degrees of informality and different intervention needs. This diversity enabled examination of how different organisational structures, working conditions, and institutional relationships affect worker experiences and support requirements.

Data collection covered interviews and field observations to ensure a comprehensive understanding of Delhi's informal waste management context and stakeholder perspectives on the support interventions. The data collection took place in November 2024, with interviews conducted at locations convenient for the participants. Four in-depth interviews were conducted with institutional stakeholders, comprising an NGO, a research group, a private sector actor, and a cooperative leader/political activist, using a semi-structured interview format, focusing on their roles in the waste sector, their contributions, perspectives on proposed interventions, and systemic barriers affecting WWs in Delhi. In-depth interviews were conducted with three sets of WWs in Delhi, comprising 10 workers with differing amounts of participation in the interview based on their availability. The interviews sought to explore the workers' lived experiences, challenges, coping strategies, and perspectives on potential support interventions. Field observations at two work sites provided contextual insights into their working conditions, daily practices, and environmental challenges.

Data Analysis

Thematic analysis was conducted using systematic coding and cross-comparison of interview transcripts and field observation notes. The analysis identified recurring themes related to current support interventions, gaps in existing systems, and stakeholder perspectives on intervention feasibility and effectiveness. Content analysis organised the findings according to the five-pathway framework, while allowing for identification of additional themes not captured in the literature-based model. The analytical approach enabled validation of the literature-based model against Delhi's practical reality, leading to model refinement incorporating context-specific insights. Cross-case comparison between different WW groups and stakeholder

perspectives provided triangulation and identification of convergent and divergent viewpoints on support intervention priorities.

Ethical Considerations and Limitations

The study ensured ethical compliance during data collection through informed consent from all participants, maintaining confidentiality and transparency throughout data collection and analysis, and conducting interviews in participants' preferred languages and settings. Particular attention was paid to power dynamics when interviewing WWs, who were approached through established community contacts serving as 'gatekeepers' for minimising feelings of exploitation or mistrust (Gibbons, 2024).

The study's focus on Delhi limits generalisability due to unique socio-cultural dynamics and policy contexts, though findings may be relevant to similar Global South urban contexts. The relatively small sample of interviews, while providing in-depth insights, may not capture the full diversity of experiences within Delhi's informal waste sector. Additionally, the absence of direct municipal government engagement limits insights into public-sector perspectives on informal WW integration. However, this reflects broader challenges in accessing government stakeholders for research on informal sector issues.

Literature-based Case Studies and Conceptual Model Development

The development of the conceptual model of support interventions for grassroots WWs followed a systematic, literature-driven approach. The aim was to analyse existing practices and derive a comprehensive framework that could address the vulnerabilities of the WWs while promoting their contribution to bringing circularity in the SWM sector. The framework was built on a review of 12 case studies from Global South countries, including Brazil, Mozambique, India, Argentina, Nigeria, Madagascar, and Ghana. These case studies were selected to identify instances where grassroots WWs were supported through specific interventions aimed at alleviating the negative externalities related to health, environment, livelihood, and dignity.

Literature-based Case Studies

Municipal integration and decent work, São Paulo, Brazil: Member-based organisations (MBOs) in São Paulo established contracts with municipalities for the collection, separation and sale of recycled materials through negotiations and advocacy (Gutberlet, 2021). The MBOs also established regulated working and rest hours, access to washrooms, running water, kitchen or refectory facilities, improving social and health benefits for the workers.

Digital platform integration, Mozambique: The Africa RISE facility piloted the Kolekt app to facilitate SWM between waste collectors, points of collection, and recycling facilities (Africa RISE, 2022). This intervention enabled ease of locating waste and valuation through the app for waste collectors while facilitating sales of waste to recycling companies (BVRIO, 2024; Sanders, 2024). The app design accommodated the participation of informal workers without requiring high levels of technological knowledge or significant financial resources.

Entrepreneurship and technology access, Nigeria: Multiple Nigerian initiatives demonstrated capacity strengthening for entrepreneurship (Ezeudu et al., 2021). The Wecyclers project designed tricycles for easy navigation of narrow streets to collect waste from underserved households, rewarding participants with redeemable points while creating employment and entrepreneurship opportunities for the WWs. The Hinckley Recycling firm recruited and trained over 2,000 WWs on safe methods of e-waste dismantling and handling through specialised training programmes, partnering with local entrepreneurs and WWs to collect scrap e-waste material for safe recycling. The Pearl Recycling enterprise created vocational skill transfer centres which trained unemployed youth in waste conversion techniques, while partnering with artisans and grassroots WWs for specialised waste collection. The OkwuEco startup created a mobile app using image recognition technology to educate households about recycling and connect them with merchants for waste trading, enabling waste collectors and dealers to identify, sort, and dispose of solid waste through an online platform.

Infrastructure and equipment, Buenos Aires, Argentina: WW cooperatives successfully lobbied for logistical support, securing access to public warehouses for processing recyclables and use of older passenger trains for transporting waste materials and equipment between the outskirts and the centre (Chen, 2018). This significantly enhanced their operations and legitimacy by providing access to formal infrastructure.

Municipal integration, Belo Horizonte, Brazil: Since 1993, city officials have included the informal sector in SWM systems involving principles of circularity (Fianoo et al., 2024). Waste sorting at the source was promoted by involving informal workers for the collection of recyclables from households and drop-off points, with state-led compensation through a 'recycling bonus' based on the amount of recycling collected (S. M. Dias, 2011; Fianoo et al., 2024). The inclusion of informal workers as cooperatives led to recognisable improvement in workers' lives over 20 years.

Cooperative integration, Pune & Bangalore, India: The Solid Waste Collection and Handling (SWaCH) cooperative in Pune demonstrates successful incorporation of the informal sector in waste management through collective action and partnerships with municipal agencies (Estrada et al., 2023). The cooperative was given charge of municipal waste collection with rights to collect

user fees from households, granting them access to public spaces for waste collection and ensuring their right to service households (Chen, 2018). Similarly, in Bangalore, Hasiru Dala, a waste picker organisation, advocated for the inclusion of informal WWs in the city's municipal SWM system by leading a study that estimated the value of their contributions, revealing that by diverting waste from landfills they saved municipal authorities around INR 230 million (approximately 2.6 million USD) (Cohen et al., 2019). This advocacy effort resulted in the registration of informal WWs with the city municipal authorities for participation in the SWM system, along with recognition of their social and economic contributions and the positive environmental impact on the city with improved segregation and recycling.

Comprehensive community support, Andralanitra Dumpsite, Madagascar: The AKAMASOA NGO provided healthcare, water and sanitation facilities to dumpsite workers engaged in scavenging, waste sorting, and compost production (Andrianisa et al., 2018). The intervention included support for the education of workers' children and facilitation of social services and housing production for the workers.

Formal Infrastructure Integration, Achimota Transfer Station, Ghana: Municipal and private actors constructed a special hub to accommodate informal WWs who used tricycles to collect and transport waste (Agyei et al., 2023). The facility provided designated tricycle parking areas and waste segregation infrastructure, reducing health and environmental risks while increasing municipal waste collection rates.

Conceptual Model Development

Common and recurring themes of support were identified and organised under five pathways of support (Appendix 1), which were adapted from Buch et al. (2021). Using the basic process model of SWM from the lens of the grassroots WWs, adapted from a figure in Scheinberg (2012), the interventions under each pathway are input into the relevant stage of the SWM process (Figure 1).

Pathway 1 - Building Networks of Stakeholders to Include WWs: Focuses on integrating WWs into formal waste networks through stakeholder collaboration, including municipal partnerships, digital platform access, and formal recognition systems.

Pathway 2 - Forming and Strengthening WW Collectives: Emphasises collective organising through cooperatives and community-based organisations that provide social security, community support, and collective bargaining power.

Pathway 3 - Capacity Strengthening for Entrepreneurship: Addresses skill development and business opportunities through training programmes, waste-based entrepreneurship access, and upskilling interventions for collection, handling, and recycling.

Pathway 4 - Access to Equipment and Technology for Remanufacturing: Focuses on the provision of technological tools, logistical support, improved workspaces, and safety equipment to enhance WW efficiency and safety.

Pathway 5 - Advocacy for Contribution of Grassroots WWs in SWM: Focuses on political and social advocacy for WW recognition, rights protection, and improvement in source waste sorting knowledge.

Figure 1. Literature-based Conceptual Model of Support Interventions for Grassroots WWs. Source: Author.

These pathways provide a structured framework for designing and implementing interventions that promote integration, equity, and sustainability within the SWM sector. Detailed in Figure 1, the framework comprehensively addresses grassroots WW integration into sustainable SWM systems while targeting their health, livelihood, environmental safety, and dignity concerns through interventions derived from Global South case studies.

Delhi Case Study: Context and Findings

The conceptual model of support interventions developed through literature analysis was tested in Delhi's grassroots-informal SWM context to assess the relevance, feasibility, and applicability of the proposed support interventions for promoting circularity in the system.

SWM Context in Delhi

Delhi's SWM system is administered by three Urban Local Bodies (ULBs): the Municipal Corporation of Delhi (MCD), New Delhi Municipal Council, and Delhi Cantonment Board (CPR, 2015). The city generates approximately 11,342 tonnes of solid waste daily, but only 66.5% of the collected waste is officially treated, with the remaining volume accumulating in landfills and dumpsites, exacerbating environmental and public health concerns (DPCC, 2024). Furthermore, the reported daily figures do not account for the unreported waste, which is beyond the reach of the formal system or is left on the streets (Jain, 2022).

This gap is addressed by grassroots WWs operating at different dimensions of informality and playing crucial roles in the SWM ecosystem. The formal waste flow is parallely followed by the informal waste flow, with MCD and contracted waste collection being complemented by informal door-to-door collectors (Delhi Urban Art Commission, 2017). Delhi's informal waste workforce was estimated between 150,000 and 200,000 (in 2010), primarily including waste pickers, small and large middlemen, and collectors, who operate at different stages of the waste value chain (Chaturvedi & Gidwani, 2010). Singh (2021) describes the informal SWM sector in Delhi as consisting of four main groups: Stage 0 recyclers who collect waste with minimal costs, Stage 1 recyclers who gather and store materials without processing, Stage 2 recyclers who manage larger quantities for later processing, and waste processors who convert scraps into secondary raw materials. Despite facing marginalisation and livelihood challenges, the informal sector workers significantly contribute to reducing transportation costs and minimising landfill use and were responsible for the recovery of around 27% of the city's recyclable waste (in 2010) (Chaturvedi & Gidwani, 2010; Gupta, 2012).

In terms of policy, several national legislations in India recognise the role of the informal sector in SWM, with the SWM Rules 2016 defining 'waste picker' in the framework and other

policies mentioning the role of the informal sector workers in the SWM sector (Chintan Environmental Research and Action Group, 2018; Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change, 2016). However, despite policy recognition, the frameworks have not resulted in sufficient measures to integrate and support the informal workforce. The introduction of privatisation in SWM rules over the last decade has had negative impacts on grassroots WWs, with studies reporting displacement and reduction in access to waste streams (Chadha, 2020; Schindler et al., 2012).

WW Groups in the Study

The study identified and approached three distinct WW groups in Delhi, who represent varying degrees of formality and organisational support, for participation in the research. Each group showcases unique operational practices and CE contributions while facing specific challenges.

Group A: Seemapuri Informal WWs

These grassroots WWs operate in one of Delhi's largest informal settlements, engaging in comprehensive waste processing activities, directly contributing to material circularity in the city's waste system. Their daily practices begin with systematic door-to-door collection from residential areas, often starting before the morning *Azan*, i.e., 5:38 AM in Delhi, before authorised collectors arrive, leveraging the trust built over years of service with the households.

The group's CE contributions centre on decentralised waste processing through neighbourhood-based sorting operations. After collection, the workers transport the waste to their neighbourhood, where they manually segregate the mixed waste streams to extract valuable materials, including metals, plastics, paper, and other recyclable components. These materials are then sold off to either Stage 2 recyclers within their neighbourhood or to recycling companies. This on-site processing creates direct material recovery pathways, which can be absent in the formal waste collection systems. When direct waste access is restricted due to the takeover by private contractors, they resort to paying these contractors a 'fee' to access the waste.

Group B, Safai Sena Cooperative Member

The interviewee represented semi-formalised WWs operating through cooperative structures that provide some organisational support while maintaining grassroots operational characteristics. As a *Safai Sena* (waste warriors in Hindi) Cooperative member, this worker

exhibits how collective organising can enhance individual WWs' capacity while preserving direct engagement with waste processing activities.

The cooperative model enables more systematic waste collection and processing through coordinated routes and shared resources. Members benefit from collective bargaining power when selling recovered materials to recyclers, potentially improving income stability compared to individual operators. However, cooperative members face similar challenges regarding equipment access, safety protection, and formal recognition as independent WWs. The organisation also serves as an intermediary organisation between individual workers and formal waste management systems.

Group C, Contract Workers

These WWs were hired workers in a public university campus, where the university had contracted a private company for SWM services on the campus. The workers were sub-contracted under this company, achieving some formalisation level in an institutional setting, while retaining informality and grassroots characteristics due to the nature of their employment and lack of social security.

These workers engage in campus-wide waste collection and processing activities under arrangements offering greater predictability compared to street-based operations. Their daily practices involve systematic collection from waste generation points, including dormitories, academic buildings, and common areas. The institutional context enables more consistent waste streams and access compared to community-based operations, while workers continue performing manual sorting and material recovery activities that generate income and contribute to resource circularity.

Barriers and Challenges Faced by WWs

The study identified multiple interconnected barriers that limit WWs' effectiveness and undermine their contributions to Delhi's CE. These challenges span institutional, economic, health, and social dimensions that collectively marginalise workers despite their essential role in resource recovery.

Privatisation of waste collection created significant access challenges for the WWs, leading to a loss of livelihood opportunities. Private companies prioritise efficiency over inclusive employment, often hiring individuals from outside Delhi rather than the existing workers. As a result, these workers face systematic exclusion from waste streams that previously provided income, forcing them to pay bribes for access, putting them in precarious and dangerous situations. The Group A workers emphasise the significance of the informal sector in this context

by highlighting the lack of segregation and material recovery conducted by private contractors, who, according to them, often prefer to bring large quantities of unsegregated waste to SWM hubs and WTE plants for combustion without segregating the recoverable waste.

The Group C workers, despite being hired by a private company, reported harassment and mistreatment to such an extent that they were on a 2-week strike before the day of the interview. Institutional non-recognition compounds these issues as workers face harassment from authorities who label their activities as illegal. The Group A and B workers often face criminalisation and bullying by authorities in the city, such as harassment from police and municipal authorities, who sometimes view their activities as illegal or problematic.

Workers also experience unpredictable daily earnings tied to waste availability and market prices for recyclables. Exploitation by middlemen during the sale of recovered materials was a key barrier for the workers. Group A workers reported that they could sell recovered plastic only at 3 rupees (approx. 0.029 EUR) per kg, which they then assumed was sold for 5-6 rupees (approx. 0.059 EUR) per kg by the middlemen to the recycling companies. Comparatively, on online scrap trade platforms in Delhi, list prices as high as 10-14 rupees (approx. 0.098-0.14 EUR) per kg.⁴ Workers often lack access to information on market prices and direct markets for recovered materials, limiting their negotiating power and reducing their share of value creation in recycling chains.

The lack of proper source segregation at the household level creates significant environmental and operational challenges for WWs. All workers reported handling mixed waste streams containing hazardous materials, organic waste, and recyclables, increasing their exposure to health risks while reducing the efficiency of material recovery processes. This contamination reduces the market value of recyclables and hinders the effectiveness of the informal circular economy, limiting potential environmental benefits from proper material recovery.

Despite significant CE contributions and pride in their work, many WWs experience deep-seated stigma that undermines their societal dignity. Several WWs reported that people often mistreat the workers and think of them as just labourers instead of people who carry out a very essential service for them. This stigma may be particularly pronounced among workers from poorer or marginal communities, further perpetuating social inequalities and limiting their recognition as professionals within the waste management ecosystem. Moreover, all the WWs reported a critical need for protective equipment due to hazardous working conditions. Many

⁴ As seen on online waste trade platforms like Delhi Kabadiwala and Kabadi Xpress (in December 2024 in the week of the interview).

WWs work with mixed waste that may include medical and electronic waste, without adequate training or protective gear, exposing them to severe health hazards.

These interconnected challenges informed the refinement of the intervention model, supporting the need for comprehensive approaches that address multiple barrier dimensions simultaneously.

Refined Model of Support Interventions

The initial conceptual model developed through Global South literature-based case study analysis required significant refinement based on the findings from Delhi. While the literature review identified broad intervention categories and pathways, studying the issues on the ground revealed gaps between theoretical frameworks and practical implementation needs that necessitated model adaptations.

The literature-based interventions often assumed the availability of institutional support mechanisms that proved either absent or inaccessible to grassroots WWs in Delhi. For example, while case studies from other cities highlighted successful integration with municipal collection systems, Delhi's privatisation trends created barriers rather than opportunities for such integration. The initial model also underestimated the complexity of accessing basic safety equipment and working spaces. Literature cases suggested equipment provision as a straightforward intervention, but Delhi findings revealed that without addressing underlying access and recognition issues, equipment alone could not address workers' vulnerabilities. Moreover, the literature-based framework inadequately addressed the interconnected nature of barriers facing Delhi's WWs, which requires coordinated approaches addressing the multiple challenges simultaneously, instead of isolated interventions.

The refined model organises support interventions under the five pathways of support that address the challenges identified in the case study (Figure 2). Appendix 2 lists which interventions were retained, modified, or excluded based on insights from stakeholders on the support which is available and the interventions which are needed. The analysis prioritised WWs' perspectives to determine the necessity of interventions, while considering feasibility and implementation aspects from the institutional stakeholders. Each pathway contains specific interventions designed for feasible implementation by the identified stakeholders, with explicit attention to sequencing and interdependencies that emerged from the case study.

Figure 2. Refined Model of Support Interventions for Grassroots WWs. Source: Author.

Pathway 1: Building Networks of Stakeholders to Include WWs

This pathway addresses the exclusion of grassroots WWs from municipal and legal processes by seeking support from institutional stakeholders such as NGOs, cooperative leaders, political activists, and formal waste companies. Support from such actors for advocacy for municipal connections, such as obtaining joint contracts directly with WW groups for waste collection and trade, can connect grassroots WWs to formal processes without seeking to formalise them, while also allowing some form of legal protection and stability in their work. Regarding the issue of identification, which was consistently identified by the participants, some WWs shared experiences of identification being issued to them by either NGOs or cooperatives. Such an intervention is recognised to support the WWs in reducing harassment and criminalisation when dealing with police or other formal authorities and would also support the workers in legitimising their contributions in the SWM sector.

Interventions for training and certification programmes are recognised to benefit WWs by formally validating their expertise and enhancing their professional recognition while fostering greater public trust in their skills. Such training can also contribute towards upskilling the workers in sustainable waste practices, supporting their participation in grassroots waste infrastructures and planning, while creating representation mechanisms in SWM decision-making forums where policies affecting WWs are developed. For such interventions, collaboration between municipal bodies, NGOs, and the research interest organisations is needed, as they would need to tailor such courses to align with the needs and skill requirements of the WWs.

Such interventions for inclusion of grassroots WWs by seeking support and collaborations with formal and institutional received strong support from study participants. Although there were some concerns that such integration might impose constraints on workers' flexibility, all participants clearly advocated for the necessity of some level of semi-formal integration.

Pathway 2: Forming and Strengthening WW Cooperatives

Based on positive experiences with collective organising of WWs in Delhi, this pathway emphasises collective action through localised, small-scale Self-Help Groups (SHGs) instead of larger organisations, that maintain worker autonomy while providing collective benefits. Interventions include support for the establishment and strengthening of such groups, and directional support for building mechanisms within the collectives for improved health and income protection for the workers. Cooperatives serve as platforms for collective bargaining with waste buyers and advocacy with authorities, while also improving working conditions of the WWs, as seen in the literature.

The second intervention emphasises the importance of local leadership development, which can support effective self-advocacy for the needs of the WWs. Moreover, engaging educated and intellectual classes is seen as vital for enhancing the collective action of WWs. Collaboration with locally influential actors, such as political leaders or student groups, can help bridge communication gaps and overcome bureaucratic hurdles, allowing WWs to advocate for systemic changes without compromising their work hours or income. This was exhibited in the workers' strike organised by Group C workers who received support from student groups to raise their issues with their contractors. NGOs and existing cooperative leaders can share implementation responsibility, building on existing social capital to create organisational foundations for other pathway interventions.

The organisation of WWs into cooperatives sparked debate, with some stakeholders doubting their feasibility in Delhi, while others advocated for cooperative efforts. A compromise emerged in the formation of localised SHGs and small-scale collectives, which could better address challenges faced by larger cooperatives, as WW groups expressed strong support for collective action and community reliance.

Pathway 3: Capacity Strengthening for Entrepreneurship

This pathway addresses workers' expressed interests in expanding economic opportunities through enhanced skills and business development. Key interventions include establishing an online marketplace for waste trade connecting WWs with potential buyers of segregated waste and waste pick-up. Such an intervention was also demonstrated by an institutional participant of the study, who ran a private company that partnered with WWs for the collection of recyclable waste and the subsequent segregation and sale of the materials to recycling companies, all facilitated through an app. To overcome challenges within such interventions, like tech illiteracy, training programmes are recommended.

Another vital intervention is the creation of a marketplace for upcycled and recycled goods, ensuring WWs find reliable buyers to support their upcycling ventures, which they would normally not have access to without external interventions. By facilitating direct collaborations between WWs and waste buyers, such interventions can help bypass exploitative middlemen, strengthened through training, ensuring fairer pricing. Training institutions and NGOs can lead implementation, with cooperatives providing organisational platforms for collective learning and peer support.

The intervention for the establishment of localised hubs for waste processing, within residential or municipal blocks, with community leadership, can further enhance income and improve waste recovery while promoting community involvement in waste management,

empowering WWs and fostering entrepreneurship at the local level. Lastly, decentralised composting interventions of organic waste can create additional income streams for WWs and reduce landfill waste.

Pathway 4: Access to Equipment and Technology for Remanufacturing and Production

Pathway 4 was significantly revised based on the case study findings that prioritised practical solutions that cater to the immediate needs of these workers over advanced technologies. The key interventions aim to improve the working conditions and efficiency of WWs through various means. The refined interventions emphasise e-rickshaw provision to WWs for improved waste collection, creating and allocating local sorting and storage spaces, and access to Material Recovery Facilities (MRFs), which are facilities recognised as centralised hubs for effective waste management.

Support from municipal subsidies and training programmes is essential to promote the adoption of the improved transport solution. The need for provision of sorting and storage spaces came across in the findings, which is recommended to be done by reallocation of underutilised public areas. For example, the Group A WWs were utilising public streets in their neighbourhood for storing and segregating their collected waste, but there was also an empty piece of municipal land, officially designated as a playground, which some of them started using for storing waste. This initiative requires effective municipal coordination to ensure these spaces are properly allocated and accessible, offering WWs safe and stable work environments.

In terms of equipment provision, the WW groups highlighted the urgent need for safer equipment, particularly air pollution masks, to address the risks of inadequate tools and hazardous working conditions, especially in Delhi's poor air quality during winter.

Pathway 5: Advocacy for Contribution of Grassroots WWs in SWM

The final pathway addresses systemic recognition and policy integration issues through advocacy for WWs' treatment and working conditions, and support for source segregation that improves their work environment. The refined approach emphasises documenting WWs' contributions to Delhi's CE through systematic research while promoting rights-based advocacy for legal protections, as seen in the case study from Bangalore.

Public awareness campaigns, aimed at schools and resident welfare associations (RWAs), aim to reduce social stigma while policy integration efforts ensure advocacy achievements translate into practical improvements. Research institutions, NGOs, and worker organisations are required to share responsibility, with sustained efforts required over longer timeframes to create enabling environments for other pathway interventions.

While advocacy for WWs through third-party actors was recognised as essential in spaces where WWs cannot represent themselves, support for self-organised advocacy by WWs emerged as equally vital. Even in advocating for improvements in source segregation, both institutional stakeholders and WWs supported initiatives enabling WW groups to share their expertise on segregation with residential organisations and schools.

The refined model emphasises the importance of recognition systems as a precondition to the success of other interventions, while fostering collective action as essential for delivering effective equipment and capacity-building interventions. Successful implementation relies on coordination mechanisms that avoid duplication and comprehensively address worker needs, adapting to the dynamic waste management landscape in Delhi. By adopting a human-centric, context-specific approach that tackles systemic gaps and incorporates stakeholder insights, the interventions promote practical solutions. Ultimately, the collaboration among municipal authorities, key stakeholders, and WWs is crucial for ensuring equitable and sustainable support for Delhi's informal WWs.

Discussion and Implications

The study underscores the importance of inclusive frameworks that not only address the structural challenges faced by WWs but also build their capacities to actively contribute to CE objectives. The integration of grassroots WWs within the municipal and institutional CE systems requires multi-faceted and localised interventions that can balance good practice examples and grounded realities of the context. The refined intervention model highlights the five pathways: stakeholder networks for integration; WW collectives; entrepreneurship training and support; infrastructure and equipment access; and policy advocacy, as critical elements in bridging the gap between informal waste ecosystems and the parallel formalised systems.

Insights from the Model

The study's findings contribute to emerging debates about inclusive CE approaches by arguing that circularity and social justice are not competing objectives but can function as mutually reinforcing elements within urban systems. The research challenges dominant CE frameworks, which may prioritise technological solutions and formal sector integration, by discussing how grassroots workers already perform essential circular functions through decentralised material recovery and processing activities. Delhi's grassroots WWs exhibit CE principles through systematic waste stream interventions that recover a considerable amount of the city's recyclable materials and even provide SWM services to the ignored parts of the city. Their door-to-door collection practices, manual segregation activities, and neighbourhood-

based (decentralised) processing operations create direct material recovery pathways that complement the formal system. These findings support theoretical arguments for bottom-up CE approaches that build on existing informal practices rather than replacing them with formal alternatives.

The study also contributes to understanding the relationship between formalisation processes and CE outcomes in SWM. It discusses how privatisation and formalisation policies can destabilise CE objectives by displacing effective informal waste recovery systems. While literature can associate formalisation with enhanced efficiency and environmental performance, Delhi's findings indicate how privatisation and formalisation processes can undermine CE effectiveness by displacing workers who perform essential material recovery functions and replacing them with a workforce unfamiliar with these practices and knowledge in that context. The shift toward privatised waste collection seemed to have reduced rather than enhanced Delhi's CE performance by limiting informal workers' access to waste streams and processing locations. This finding suggests that waste management privatisation policies require explicit provisions for the grassroots WW inclusion to maintain CE effectiveness. However, these insights emerge from Delhi's specific privatisation experience and may not apply directly to other socio-political contexts.

A key finding of Delhi's case study is the potential for collaboration between diverse stakeholders, including municipal bodies, private sector actors, NGOs, and WW cooperatives. The examples of successful partnerships, such as those facilitated by NGOs and Safai Sena in Delhi, illustrate possibilities for collective action to enhance working conditions and increase the efficiency of waste recovery. However, the effectiveness of such collaborations is contingent on clear policy directives, robust enforcement mechanisms, and the active participation of all stakeholders.

Hence, the study supports the argument that collective organisation is essential for sustainable grassroots worker empowerment. Cooperative structures, like Safai Sena, in Delhi showcase how collective action can enhance individual workers' capacity while creating organisational foundations for sustainable intervention delivery. The cooperative model can enable collective procurement and shared resource management and strengthen the bargaining power that individual workers (Group A) cannot achieve independently, while maintaining workers' autonomy and direct engagement with waste processing activities. However, the research also reveals limitations of cooperative approaches in contexts of large, diverse groups, leading to recommendations for localised neighbourhood-level groups to meet the needs of the workers within the group, while providing a joint platform for collective action.

Moreover, the necessity of institutional collaboration as a prerequisite for other interventions emerged as a key finding. Delhi's WWs' experience with criminalisation and institutional exclusion makes evident how the lack of recognition creates cascading barriers that undermine access to equipment, training, financial services, and advocacy support. This finding highlights the importance of rights-based approaches to supporting informal workers, underscoring the foundational role of institutional recognition in facilitating comprehensive support delivery.

The assessment of equipment and safety interventions as immediate priority needs, such as the Delhi workers' unanimous requests for basic protective equipment, reveals how fundamental safety needs must be addressed to enable participation in other intervention activities. This finding supports the use of multi-dimensional support approaches that combine immediate practical support with longer-term empowerment strategies.

Research Contributions

The research contributes to the literature on just transitions in CE by exhibiting how CE transitions can either enhance or undermine social equity depending on their design and implementation approaches. Delhi's case indicates that CE transitions that ignore existing grassroots practices risk creating unjust outcomes that displace vulnerable workers while potentially reducing environmental effectiveness. Delhi workers' detailed knowledge of waste flows, processing techniques, and market dynamics represents essential expertise for effective CE system design. Moreover, their overarching motivation of improving their lived environment through their work, along with knowledge for sustainable consumption and production practices for reducing unsustainable waste production, positions them as direct CE practitioners rather than passive beneficiaries. However, the study also reveals significant challenges in implementing such transitions, which would require balancing between individual worker empowerment and systemic change objectives. While support interventions can enhance individual workers' capacity and conditions, addressing systemic marginalisation requires broader policy and institutional changes that affect power relations within urban waste management systems.

The study's methodological approach contributes to informal CE research by highlighting the value of participatory case study methods that centre the WWs' perspectives while incorporating multiple stakeholder viewpoints. The combination of literature review, institutional stakeholder interviews, and WW consultations enabled a comprehensive understanding of intervention feasibility from multiple perspectives while maintaining focus on grassroots needs and priorities. Moreover, the model refinement process indicates how empirical testing can enhance

theoretical frameworks by revealing implementation barriers and contextual factors that affect intervention effectiveness. The substantial differences between literature-based and empirically refined models highlight the importance of context-specific adaptation in intervention design rather than direct application of global good practices.

The study also highlights the broader implications of including grassroots WWs into CE systems. Beyond the immediate benefits of social inclusion and economic empowerment, such interconnection between the formal and informal sectors is critical for advancing sustainability goals for effective SWM and circular use of resources. Informal WWs are central to resource recovery in several Global South cities, and their marginalisation risks undermining CE initiatives. By adopting localised and inclusive strategies, policymakers can create a more equitable and effective transition to CE while addressing systemic inequities in labour and resource management.

Study Limitations

The study has methodological limitations that impact the generalisability of the findings. The focus solely on Delhi restricts the understanding of how local factors influence intervention feasibility in other contexts, suggesting that additional case studies would enhance insights into the effectiveness of such interventions across diverse socio-political and economic contexts. Additionally, while qualitative methods offer rich perspectives on worker experiences and stakeholder views, future research could benefit from mixed methods that integrate qualitative insights and quantitative measurements of environmental, economic, and social outcomes. Lastly, the study's limited timeframe hinders an understanding of the long-term effectiveness and sustainability of interventions, indicating the need for extended longitudinal research to better assess their impact on worker outcomes and CE application.

Conclusion

The study aimed to examine how informal CE at the grassroots-level can be supported through targeted interventions for grassroots WWs, using Delhi as a case study. It highlighted the critical role that the informal sector actors play in driving circularity within SWM systems in the Global South, where formal systems have not been able to fully absorb their contributions. Using a combination of case studies from literature and empirical data from Delhi, the research developed a model of support interventions comprising five interconnected pathways of support interventions. The findings from the Delhi case study suggest that enhancing the livelihoods, dignity, and working conditions of WWs can meaningfully contribute towards maintaining urban circularity and ensuring just transitions to CE in such a context.

The model underscores the importance of stakeholder collaboration, collective organisation, capacity building, access to technology, and policy advocacy as key pathways for including WWs in formal systems. The findings from Delhi support the potential effectiveness of small-scale, decentralised support interventions that leverage local knowledge and address the systemic challenges faced by the grassroots WWs while aligning with broader sustainability goals.

The support intervention model developed through the study argues for the value of bottom-up interventions that respond to local socio-economic contexts, along with the integration of state and top-down actors. Such an approach may not only empower marginalised workers but also potentially strengthen CE systems by leveraging the expertise and contributions of those most directly involved in resource recovery.

As countries in the Global South strive to transition to CE, the integration of grassroots WWs may represent both a sustainability and a social justice imperative based on the insights from the Delhi case study. Future research should explore the scalability of the proposed model, examining its application in other urban contexts and its potential to inform Global South policy frameworks. Additional case studies across different contexts would be necessary to validate these preliminary findings. By focusing on the voices and needs of informal workers, policymakers can potentially foster inclusive and resilient systems that advance sustainability while promoting equity and justice.

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Conflict of interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Literature-based Model for Support Interventions for Grassroots WWs in SWM systems Conceptual Model for Support Interventions

	Interventions	Cases	Externality targeted	Actors involved	Examples
Path-ways of Support P1. Building Networks of Stakeholders to Include Ws	1.1: Access to marketplace for waste.	Mozambique (Kolekt app), Nigeria (OkwuEco app)	Environment, Livelihood, Dignity	NGOs Tech Startups WW Cooperatives	Development of app which increases access to a marketplace/online trading platforms for direct sales of waste to recycling companies
	1.2: Access to waste supply chains.	Sao Paulo, Brazil; Belo Horizonte, Brazil; Bangalore, India	Livelihood, Dignity	NGOs WW Cooperatives Public sector SWM agencies	Integrating informal workers in municipal waste collection networks; Registration of WWs for formal SWM participation
P2. Forming and Strengthening WW Cooperatives	2.1: Provision of, or inclusion in social security.	Sao Paulo, Brazil	Health, Livelihood, Dignity	WW Cooperatives Public sector SWM agencies	Sao Paulo's MBOs provided social benefits for informal workers such as sick leaves through negotiations with public sector agencies.
	2.2: Community building interventions.	Andralanitra Dumpsite, Madagascar	Health, Livelihood, Dignity	NGOs	Long term community-based interventions by the NGO, such as social services, counselling and guidance in community-based issues.
P3. Capacity Strengthening for Entrepreneurship	3.1: Access to opportunities for waste-based entrepreneurship.	Lagos, Nigeria (Wecyclers); Nigeria (Hinckley Recycling); Nigeria (Pearl Recycling)	Environment, Livelihood	WW Cooperatives Private actors Social Enterprises	Incentivising and rewarding recycling with redeemable points; Opportunities for safe e-waste disposal and entrepreneurial partnerships,
	3.2: Upskilling interventions for waste collection, handling, segregation, and recycling.	Nigeria (Hinckley Recycling); Belo Horizonte, Brazil	Environment, Livelihood	NGOs Private actors Public sector SWM agencies	Trainings for safer waste handling/dismantling training, Trainings for sorting and recycling knowledge.

P4. Access to Equipment and Technology for Remanufacturing and Production	4.1: Access to innovative technologies for identification and valuation of waste.	4.2: Access to logistic support and equipment.	4.3: Participation of WWs in innovative changes.	4.4: Provision of improved workspaces.	4.5: Provision of waste management equipment.	4.6: Provision of health and safety equipment.	5.1: Advocacy for contribution of grassroots workers in SWM.	5.2: Improvement in source waste sorting and recycling knowledge.	P5. Advocacy for grassroots workers in SWM
Mozambique (Kolekt app), Nigeria (OkwuEco app)	Buenos Aires, Arg. (public infr. for waste transport); Lagos, Nig. (tricycles for waste coll.); Greater Accra, Ghana (tricycle supp. at waste coll. hub)	Mozambique (Kolekt app), Nigeria (Pearl Recycling)	Sao Paulo, Brazil; Greater Accra, Ghana; Buenos Aires, Argentina	Lagos, Nigeria (Wecyclers); Greater Accra Region, Ghana	Sao Paulo, Brazil; Andralanitra Dumpsite, Madagascar	Sao Paulo, Brazil; Buenos Aires, Argentina; Pune, India	Lagos, Nigeria; Bangalore, India; Belo Horizonte, Brazil	Health, Environment, Livelihood, Dignity	App to help waste collectors locate, assess, and sell waste; App uses image recognition for waste identification, enabling waste trading and valuation.
Access to public warehouses and trains for waste transport; Provision of innovative tricycles for household waste collection in difficult to reach areas; Infrastructure for tricycle parking and waste weighing	Co-production of app for waste collection etc./marketplace with piloting on WWs; WWs involved in recycling and production of items from waste for retail	Access to formal infrastructure for recycling/sorting; Provision of sanitation facilities at dumpsites	Private sector provision of innovative tricycles for collection of waste; Inclusion in formal SWM infrastructure at collection hubs for informal workers such as dedicated lane, parking and waste weighing facilities.	Provision of PPE for safe collection, handling, dismantling of waste, and for health concerns of WWs; Provision of sanitation and health services to WWs	Political and social advocacy for WWs' recognition and rights in SWM systems, through engagement with key actors and research on positive contributions to the city.	Incentivizes waste sorting at the household level; Raising awareness on waste segregation.	Private actors Public sector SWM agencies	NGOs Development Assistance Agencies Private Actors (Tech Startups)	Cooperation of WWs and NGOs; Provision of formal infrastructure for recycling/sorting; Provision of sanitation facilities at dumpsites
Health, Environment, Livelihood, Dignity	Environment, Livelihood, Dignity	Environment, Livelihood, Dignity	Health, Dignity	Environment, Livelihood	Health, Dignity	Livelihood, Dignity	Environment, Livelihood	Private actors Public sector SWM agencies	Cooperation of WWs and NGOs; Provision of formal infrastructure for recycling/sorting; Provision of sanitation facilities at dumpsites
Private actors Public sector SWM agencies	NGOs Development Assistance Agencies Private Actors (Tech Startups)	NGOs Social Enterprises Development Assistance Agencies	NGOs WW Cooperatives Public sector SWM agencies	WW Cooperatives Public sector SWM agencies	NGOs WW Cooperatives Public sector SWM agencies	NGOs WW Cooperatives Public sector SWM agencies	NGOs WW Cooperatives Public sector SWM agencies	NGOs WW Cooperatives Public sector SWM agencies	Political and social advocacy for WWs' recognition and rights in SWM systems, through engagement with key actors and research on positive contributions to the city.
NGOs Development Assistance Agencies Private Actors (Tech Startups)	NGOs Social Enterprises Development Assistance Agencies	NGOs WW Cooperatives Public sector SWM agencies	WW Cooperatives Public sector SWM agencies	NGOs WW Cooperatives Public sector SWM agencies	NGOs WW Cooperatives Public sector SWM agencies	NGOs WW Cooperatives Public sector SWM agencies	NGOs WW Cooperatives Public sector SWM agencies	NGOs Private actors Public sector SWM agencies	Political and social advocacy for WWs' recognition and rights in SWM systems, through engagement with key actors and research on positive contributions to the city.
Political and social advocacy for WWs' recognition and rights in SWM systems, through engagement with key actors and research on positive contributions to the city.	Incentivizes waste sorting at the household level; Raising awareness on waste segregation.								

Appendix 2: Refined Model for Support Interventions for Grassroots WWs in SWM systems:

Pathway	Old Intervention		New Intervention	Stakeholders Supporting	Status
Building Networks of Stakeholders to Include WWs	Access to marketplace for waste.	1.1	Contracts with Municipal Authorities for Semi-formal Inclusion in SWM System	NGO, Research Interest Organisation, WW groups	Updated
	Access to waste supply chains.	1.2	Systematic Enumeration and Issuance of ID Cards	NGO, Research Interest Organisation, WW groups, Political Activist group	Updated
		1.3	Trainings and Skill Certificate	NGO, Research Interest Organisation, WWs with Safai Sena	New
Forming and Strengthening WW Collectives	Provision of, or inclusion in social security.	2.1	Social Security Mechanisms for Health and Income Protection	WW groups, Political Activist, Research Interest Organisation	Updated
	Community building interventions.	2.2	Support for Local Leadership Development	NGO, Research Interest Organisation, WW groups, Political Activist group	Updated
		2.3	Support for Localised WW Collectives or SHGs	NGO, Research Interest Organisation, WW with Safai Sena, WWs in Seemapuri, Political Activist group	Updated
		2.4	Support from Educated and Intellectual Classes for Collective Action	Political Activist group, Research Interest Organisation, WW in public university and Seemapuri	Updated
Capacity Strengthening for Entrepreneurship	Access to opportunities for waste-based entrepreneurship.	3.1	Online Marketplace for Waste Trade	NGO, Research Interest Organisation, Private Company, WWs in Seemapuri	Updated
		3.2	Marketplace for Upcycled and Recycled Goods	WWs in Seemapuri, WWs in a public university, Political Activist	Updated
		3.3	Partnerships for Valuable Scrap Collection	Private Company, NGO, Research Interest Organisation, WWs in a public university, WWs in Seemapuri	Updated
		3.4	Localised Facilities for Waste Processing	WW groups. NGO, Research Interest Organisation, Political Activist, Private Company	Updated
		3.5	Ward- Based Waste Management Pilots	WWs with Safai Sena, NGO, Political Activist	Updated
		3.6	Decentralised composting of organic waste	WWs with Safai Sena, NGO, WWs in Seemapuri	Updated
		3.7	Support for transition to innovative entrepreneurship	WW groups, Political Activist, Private Company, NGO	New

Pathway	Old Intervention		New Intervention	Stakeholders Supporting	Status
	Upskilling interventions for waste collection, handling, segregation, and recycling.	3.8	Training for Developing Tech Literacy	Private Company, WW groups, Research Interest Organisation	Updated
		3.9	Knowledge Building to Avoid Exploitation	WWs in Seemapuri, WWs in a public university, Political Activist, NGO, Research Interest Organisation	New
Access to Infrastructure and Equipment for Remanufacturing and Production	Access to innovative technologies for identification and valuation of waste.				Removed
	Access to logistic support and equipment.	4.1	Transition to E-Rickshaws for Waste Collection	WW groups	Updated
		4.2	Supporting and Implementing E-Rickshaw Use	WW groups	Updated
	Participation of waste workers in innovative changes.				Removed
	Provision of improved workspaces.	4.3	Provision of Local Sorting and Storage Spaces	WW groups, NGO, Research Interest Organisation, Political Activist, Private Company	Updated
	Provision of waste management equipment.	4.4	Access to MRFs	WW in Safai Sena, NGO, Research Interest Organisation	Updated
	Provision of health and safety equipment.	4.5	Distribution of Safety Gear	WW groups, NGO, Research Interest Organisation, Political Activist	Updated
		4.6	Provision of Air Pollution Masks	WW groups, NGO, Research Interest Organisation, Political Activist	Added
Advocacy for Contribution of WWs in SWM	Advocacy for contribution of grassroots workers in SWM.	5.1	Advocacy for Treatment and Working Conditions of WWs	WW groups, NGO, Research Interest Organisation, Political Activist, Private Company	Updated
	Improvement in source waste sorting and recycling knowledge.	5.2	Support for source segregation	WW groups, NGO, Research Interest Organisation, Political Activist, Private Company	Updated